

Recasting Democracy in Education through Commons

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In recent years, democracy has been seriously undermined, leading to widespread disaffection with the political system. The global economic crisis since 2008 has brought about extensive impoverishment, insecurity, precarity, and indebtedness. Precarity and exclusion are predominantly experienced through a certain individualism, which often engenders individual and collective impotence. From 1990 onwards, a post-democratic consensus was made solid in liberal democracies worldwide. The spread of a consumerist, a-political individualism among citizens has coalesced with the attachment of ruling parties to the neoliberal doctrine as the sole reasonable option for a developed and prospering economy. In this context, the treatment of education issues as solely technical questions, the increasing authority of experts, the eclipse of real choices within the education system are trademarks of an impoverished form of (post)democracy dominated by elites (Crouch, 2004; Mouffe, 2005).

In this short text, I discuss how education has responded to these conditions of material and political disempowerment, the alienation from mainstream politics, and the hollowing out of democracy. The turn towards new modes of collective self-organization, the attempt to construct new social bonds and to forge socially empowered forms of subjectivity in the field of education should be understood in relation to the current critical political and social context. However, before embarking on account of alternative democratic politics in education in such circumstances, it is necessary to engage with the political concept.

A significant predicament when looking into democracy and politics in education today is the conventional understanding of the relationship between children, youth, and the political. A pervasive problem with the mainstream participation literature is that “a restrictive conception of politics leads to a restrictive understanding of participation” (McCaffrie & Marsh, 2013). A narrow understanding of democratic politics and participation

locates education and the people involved in it only in terms of the formal political system: elections, voters, and representatives. The student council is “a clear example of participation based on liberal democratic principles” (Wyness, 2018, p.55). Hence, if democracy in education is seen through standard, adult-driven systemic lenses, much of what can count as students’ and pupils’ political engagement will be either missed altogether or dismissed as irrelevant. Focusing on conventional forms of activity and organization (voting, representation, etc.) would tend to confirm the thesis of young people’s apathy or apoliticism and children’s political lack and inability. Consequently, the debate over the relation between democracy and education cannot advance without reconsidering our conception(s) of “the political”.

Traditionally, politics has been identified with the apparatus of a nation-state: the cabinet, the parliament, political parties, public administration, etc. (Heywood, 2013). This conception of politics has been increasingly contested in the twentieth century. Several strands of contemporary political theory (Connolly, 1995; Day, 2005; Mouffe, 2005; Rancière, 2010), sociology (Giddens, 1991; Beck, 1992), and anthropology (Scott, 1990) have pushed the “decentering” of the political further away from its concentration on the state. They have removed the emphasis on “institution”. Also, they have located the political in every act and process that struggles over established social forms and structures, seeking to contest them, transform them, or uphold them. Moreover, they have blurred the distinction between ordinary and extraordinary politics, conventional and unconventional, visible and invisible. Kioupkiolis and Pechtelidis (2017) introduced the term “Heteropolitics” to underscore that ‘the political’ as a deliberate collective action on social structures and subjectivities can also be part of ordinary, face-to-face interactions and attempts at coping with everyday problems.

Departing from such diverse conceptions of the political, “education” is construed as political and ethical activity

which deliberately intervenes in actual social relations, structures and embedded subjectivities – i.e. conventional modes of thought, understanding, evaluation, motivation, feeling, action and interaction – by resisting, challenging, transfiguring or striving to preserve them.

The emergent paradigm of the “commons” is a promising alternative for deepening democracy in the field of education; in other words, for refiguring education, and for social change in general, on a footing of equality, sharing, participation, togetherness, caring, and freedom. The educational commons involve the co-production, distribution, and collective ownership of knowledge in non-formal, informal, and formal learning spaces, like classrooms, that share space for collaboration, project-work, content creation, meetings, socialization, playing, and studying. In the educational commons, the community of people building them can intervene in governing their interaction processes and their shared resources. Educational commons provide the community with free and easy access to knowledge and information, reinforcing intercultural and intergenerational dialogue and social inclusion, develop essential social and personal skills for both children and adults, establish spaces of democratic citizenship (Pechtelidis, 2018; Pechtelidis & Kioupiolis, 2020).

In a commons-oriented education, understanding children and young people as social actors is crucial for how they become visible and their contribution to knowledge production and their participation in the decision-making processes. Furthermore, evaluation becomes a democratic common process and (provisional) decision in which people are active participants. They must take responsibility – not delegating responsibility to the experts, registrars, and inspectors. Here pedagogical documentation can work as a tool for evaluation, which is perceived as a collective meaning-making process rather than a technical practice. This methodology not only can make pedagogical work visible, but also subject to interpretation and argumentation within a community of participants. Pedagogical documentation as an ethico-political practice strives to avoid closure by opening up the evaluation and self-conduct to debate and contestation (Dahlberg & Moss, 2005).

A commons-based democratic education should do four things: a. challenging the dominant discourses about the role of education, inclusion, childhood & youth,

evaluation, and hence opening up dialogue and allowing difference to exist in its own terms; b. transgressing the normative frameworks about childhood and youth; c. undermining governmentality – children and adults being governed less, and opening up to new possibilities for fewer inequalities; d. learning through co-constructing knowledge.

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